

COMMUNICATION BARRIERS BETWEEN NURSES AND PATIENTS DURING HOSPITALIZATION IN PMCH NAWABSHAH

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Abstract

Background: Good communication between nurses and patients is very important for good treatment. If communication is not clear, it can cause confusion, stress, and slow recovery at PMCH Nawabshah, nurses face problems like language differences, less time, and too much work. Effective communication between nurses and patients plays a crucial role in the delivery of quality healthcare services, especially when caring for patients from diverse cultural backgrounds. It fosters trust, understanding, and collaboration and contributes to better health outcomes and satisfactory nurse–patient relationships. Several barriers come in between like Cultural differences, heavy workload, lack of cultural competence, and limited resources were major barriers to nurse–patient communication in multicultural hospital settings. This aim of study wants to find out the common problems in communication between nurses and patients and how these problems affect patient care and satisfaction.

Methodology: This study was a cross sectional, in which non-probability convenience sampling method was used and conducted from November 2025 to January 2026 at College of Nursing Female Nawabshah, sample size of this study was 384 divided in both nurses 192 and patients 192.

Results: Main problems include language issues, cultural differences, and heavy workload. These problems can reduce patient satisfaction and cause misunderstanding. The most barriers are Age difference among nurses and patients, nurses' data (37.9±5.9), and patient's data (42.9±15.1), was the most common barriers to the nurses-patients communication the gender differences among nurses and patients, nurses were majority of male (55.61%), and patients female (78.13%), was the most important berries. The most important barrier average number of per patients were (22.3±23.7).

Conclusion: Communication barriers, language and workload issues, affect the nurses-patient's relationships at PMCH Nawabshah, and addressing these challenges can improve the patient satisfaction and the care Quality.

Introduction

Effective communication between nurses and patients plays a crucial role in the delivery of

quality healthcare services, especially when caring for patients from diverse cultural backgrounds.¹ It fosters trust, understanding, and collaboration

and contributes to better health outcomes and satisfactory nurse–patient relationships.² Several barriers come in between like Cultural differences, heavy workload, lack of cultural competence, and limited resources were major barriers to nurse–patient communication in multicultural hospital settings.³ One of the biggest barrier is language difference and the hospital do not have the proper interpreter services and the other issues such as too much Noise, too much disturbance in hospital, family’s interruption so that nurses become overloaded and stressed.⁴ Nurses reported barriers related to emotional imbalance, organizational factors, cultural awareness, and both patient and environmental factors played roles in ineffective communication.⁵ Staff shortages, time constraints, nurse fatigue, and high patient loads were the main communication barriers in emergency departments.⁶ In ICU it’s more difficult to manage because patients are unconscious in ICU at that time family interruption, too much noise can make nurses over stressed and made them difficult to focus on their work.⁷ Nurses identified job-related factors (workload, lack of time) as major barriers, while patients highlighted nurse aggressiveness and age differences.⁸ More ever, a person who does not understand the common language of hospital can face many medical challenges and poor care management. Poor communication was associated with lack of formal training, high workload, and nurses’ lower education level or experience.⁹ 78% of patients perceived barriers; significant factors included age, education, marital status, and family type, alongside environmental and nurse-related barriers.¹⁰ Students identified nurse-related, patient-related, and hierarchy-related barriers; communicating with nurses was more challenging than with patients.¹¹ Nursing students with high communication apprehension avoided patient interaction, negatively impacting therapeutic communication.¹² Both nurses and patients identified time constraints, nurse workload, patient health status, and environmental noise as significant obstacles to effective communication.¹³ Patients reported nurse shortage, language barriers, negative attitudes, and lack of motivation as key communication barriers.

² Language and cultural differences, inadequate infrastructure, and negative nurse attitudes were linked to poor therapeutic communication and adverse patient outcomes.¹⁴ Nurses reported suboptimal communication due to time pressure, patient overload, and interference from family members.¹⁵ Nurses cited fatigue, workload, and lack of privacy as major obstacles to meaningful patient communication.¹⁶ Barriers stemmed from organizational constraints, nurse attitudes, patient literacy, and environmental interruptions.¹⁷ In Saudi Arabia and Bahrain, the main barrier is language so during Covid 19 masks and restricted visitors make the communication even harder specially for person who has disabilities. In Pakistan specially in PMCH Nawabshah these problems are more triggers.¹⁸ In the context of Pakistan, particularly in public sector hospitals such as PMCH Nawabshah, these barriers may be even more pronounced due to limited resources, cultural diversity, and high patient loads. Exploring communication barriers in PMCH Nawabshah will provide essential insights for improving patient-centred care in the local context.

Objectives: To identify the barriers to effective nurse–patient communication during hospitalization at PMCH Nawabshah. To explore the impact of communication barriers on patient outcomes and satisfaction.

Aim of study: This aim of study wants to find out the common problems in communication between nurses and patients and how these problems affect patient care and satisfaction.

Material and methods This study was cross sectional study, which is conducted from November 2025 to January 2026 at PMCH Nawabshah. The non-probability convenient sampling technique was used. The sample size was determined using the Rao-soft sample size calculator at a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, 50% response distribution, and a target population of 384 divided in both nurses and patients. The required sample size was calculated as both nurses 192 and patients 192.

Inclusion Criteria

- Registered nurses working at least 1 year at PMCH Nawabshah and patients admitted in hospital in PMCH Nawabshah.
- Gender: male and female both nurses and patients
- Age: for patient above 18-60 years
- Age: for nurses aged above 20-60 years

Exclusion Criteria

- Nurses resign their job and there are leave and the patients are discharged and those which unconscious condition.

Tools for Data Collection:

A self structured questionnaire was used in this study, two questionnaires used: For Nurses: It was asked about workload, language issues, cultural problems, and support from the hospital For Patients: It was asked about how clearly nurses communicate, whether patients feel satisfied, and if they understand the treatment plan. Before

starting data collection, permission was taken from the hospital administration. Informed consent was also obtained from all cooperatives, nurses and patients, after clarifying the purpose of the study and convincing them that their information was kept private. Data was collected through a self-structured questionnaire that includes closed-ended questions. For nurses, the questionnaires were self-administered during their duty hours, while for patients, an interviewer helped fill out the form because some of them not able to read or write. The questionnaire focused on different factors that affect communication during hospitalization, such as language barrier, cultural differences, education level, workload, time limitation, attitude and environmental factors. Data was analyzed using basic descriptive statistics: Frequencies and percentages were calculated for demographic variables. To analyze communication barriers and patient satisfaction. Furthermore, Chi -Square test, and correlations were used to find out the relationship between communication barriers and patient satisfaction. , and ($p < .05$) kept significant.

Table no. 1 AGE OF SUBJECT

Nurses Results		Patients Results	
Mean	37.9063	Mean	42.9896
St. Deviation	5.98266	St. Deviation	15.19713
Minimum	30	Minimum	20
Maximum	60	Maximum	90

Distribution of age of subject among nurses and patients were, nurses mean (37. 9±S.D 5.9), minimum (30 years) maximum (60), and patient were mean (42.9, ± S.D 15.1), minimum (20), maximum (90).

Figure no 1 SUBJECT OF GENDER

Distribution of gender among nurses were (44.79%) female, (55.21%) male, and patients were (21.88%) male, (78.13%) female.

Table no 02 SUBJECT OF MARITAL STATUS

PATIENT RESULT				NURSES RESULT			
		Frequency	Percent			Frequency	Percent
Valid	Single	58	30.2	Valid	single	28	14.6
	Married	126	65.6		Married	161	83.9
	widow	8	4.2		widow	3	1.6
	Total	192	100.0		Total	192	100.0

Distribution of subject of marital status patients were, single 58(30.2%), married 126(65.6%), widow 8(4.2%), and nurses were, single 28(14.6%), widow 3(1.6%).

TABLE NO. 03. SUBJECT OF EDUCATION

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	No education	114	59.4
	Primary	52	27.1
	Secondary	16	8.3
	Higher	10	5.2
	Total	192	100.0

Distribution of subject or education patient were no education 114 (59.4%), primary 52 (27.1%), secondary 16(8.3%) and higher 10(5.2%) total population 192(100.0%).

TABLE NO. 04. SUBJECT OF STAY IN HOSPITAL PATIENTS

Valid	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	maximum
192	5.3177	3.92043	1.00	20.00

Duration of hospital stay among study subjects reported (5.31±S.D 3.9) with minimum stay 1 Day, and maximum 20 days.

TABLE NO.05. SUBJECT OF YEARS OF NURSING EXPERIENCE

Valid	Mean	St. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
192	7.4479	5.94190	1.00	32.00

Distribution of subject of years of nursing experience among study reported (7.44± S.D 5.94), minimum 1 year, maximum 32 years.

TABLE NO.06. SUBJECT OF AVERAGE NUMBER OF PATIENT PER SHIFT NURSES RESULT

Valid	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	maximum
192	22.3229	23.74846	3.00	300.00

Distribution of subjects of average number of patients per shift nurses were, (22.3, ±S.D 23.7), minimum 3, maximum 300.

TABLE NO. 07. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH NURSES AGE OF SUBJECT (RESULT OF PATIENT)

S No	Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	P Value
1	I understand what nurses tell me about my illness	3 (1.56%)	16 (8.33%)	8 (2.60%)	99 (51.56%)	66 (34.37%)	.021
2	Nurses explain my medicines clearly	7 (3.64%)	11 (5.72%)	7 (3.64%)	118 (61.45%)	49 (25.52%)	.028
3	Nurses give me enough time to ask questions	4 (2.08%)	17 (8.85%)	11 (5.72%)	86 (44.79%)	74 (38.54%)	.043
4	I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses	5 (2.60%)	8 (4.16%)	33 (17.18%)	108 (56.25%)	38 (19.79%)	.023
5	Nurses respect my privacy during care	5 (2.60%)	13 (6.77%)	7 (3.64%)	80 (41.66%)	87 (45.31%)	.025
6	Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses	6 (3.12%)	33 (17.18%)	18 (9.37%)	98 (51.04%)	37 (19.27%)	.034
7	The Ward environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult	4 (2.08%)	17 (8.85%)	19 (9.89%)	121 (63.02%)	31 (16.14%)	.030
8	Nurses listen to my concerns show care	4 (2.08%)	19 (9.89%)	4 (2.08%)	104 (54.16%)	61 (31.77%)	.005
9	Overall, I am satisfied with nurse's communication	4 (2.08%)	13 (6.77%)	12 (6.25%)	78 (40.62%)	84 (43.75%)	.005

- Item no.01. I understand what nurses tell me about my illness. Were strongly disagree 3 (1.56%), Disagree 16(8.33%), Neutral 8 (2.60%), Agree 99(51.56%), Strongly agree 66 (34.37%), $P = .021$.
- Item no.02. Nurses explain my medicines clearly. Were strongly disagree 7(3.64%), Disagree 11(5.72%), Neutral 7(3.64%), Agree 118(61.45%), strongly agree 49 (25.52%), $p = .028$.
- Item no.03. Nurses give me enough time to ask questions. Were Strongly disagree 4 (2.08%), Disagree 17 (18.85%), Neutral 11 (5.72%), Agree 86(44.79%), Strongly agree 74(38.54%), $p = .043$
- Item no.04. I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses. Were

strongly disagree 5(2.60%), Disagree 8 (4.16%), Neutral 33 (17.18%), Agree 108 (56.25%), Strongly agree 38 (19.79%), $P = .023$.

- Item no.5. Nurses respect my privacy during care. Were Strongly Disagree 5(2.60%), Disagree 13 (6.77%), Neutral 7 (3.64%), Agree 80 (41.66%), Strongly agree 87 (45.31%), $P = .025$.
- Item no.6. Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses. Were Strongly Disagree 6 (3.12%), Disagree 33 (17.18%), Neutral 18 (9.37%), Agree 98 (51.04%), Strongly agree 37 (19.27%), $P = .034$.
- Item no.7. The ward environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult. Were Strongly Disagree 4 (2.08%), Disagree

17 (8.85%), Neutral 19 (9.89%), Agree 121 (63.02%), Strongly agree 31 (16.14%), $P = .030$.

- Item no.8. Nurses listen to my concerns show care. Were Strongly Disagree 4(2.08%), Disagree 19 (9.89%), Neutral 4 (2.08%),

Agree 104 (54.16%), Strongly agree 61 (31.77%), $P = .005$.

- Item no.9. Overall, I am satisfied with nurse's communication. Were Strongly Disagree 4(2.08%), Disagree 13 (6.77%), Neutral 12 (6.25%), Agree 78 (40.62%), Strongly agree 86(43.755%), $P = .005$.

TABLE NO.08. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH PATIENTS SUBJECT OF AGE (NURSES RESULT)

S No	Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	P Value
1	I face language problems while communicating with patients.	29 (15.10%)	31 (16.14%)	46 (23.95%)	66 (34.37%)	20 (10.43%)	.174
2	Heavy workload affects my communication with patients.	17 (8.85%)	30 (15.62%)	35 (18.22%)	86 (44.79%)	24 (12.5%)	.021
3	Cultural or religious differences create difficulties.	10 (5.20%)	48 (25%)	38 (19.79%)	53 (27.60%)	43 (22.39%)	.600
4	The hospital environment (noise, privacy issues) makes communication difficult.	17 (8.85%)	21 (10.93%)	46 (23.955)	75 (39.06%)	33 (17.18%)	.029
5	Masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly.	20 (10.41%)	53 (27.60%)	30 (15.62%)	57 (29.68%)	32 (16.66%)	.446
6	Patients' family members interfere in communication	21 (10.93%)	32 (16.66%)	35 (18.22%)	76 (39.58%)	28 (14.58%)	.223
7	I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures.	8 (4.16%)	21 (10.93%)	24 (12.5%)	84 (43.75%)	55 (28.64%)	.006
8	I receive support from doctors for effective communication.	15 (7.81%)	21 (10.93%)	30 (15.62%)	75 (39.06%)	51 (26.56%)	.464
9	I have received training in communication skills	3 (1.56%)	33 (17.18%)	30 (15.62%)	72 (37.5%)	54 (28.12%)	.796
10	Overall, my communication with patients is effective	0	14 (7.29%)	14 (7.29%)	49 (25.52%)	114 (59.37%)	.012

- Item no.1. I feel language problems while communicating with patients. Were Strongly Disagree 29 (15.10%), Disagree 31 (16.14%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 66 (34.37%), Strongly agree 20 (10.43%), $P = .174$.
- Item no.2. Heavy workload affects my communication with patients. Were Strongly Disagree 17 (8.85%), Disagree 30

(15.62%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 86 (44.79%), Strongly agree 24 (12.5%), $P = .021$.

- Item no.3. Cultural or religious differences create difficulties. Were Strongly Disagree 10 (5.20%), Disagree 48 (25%), Neutral 38 (19.79%), Agree 53 (27.60%), Strongly agree 43 (22.39%), $P = .600$.

- Item no.4. The hospital environment (noise, privacy issues) makes it difficult. Were Strongly Disagree 17 (8.85%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 75 (39.06%), Strongly agree 33 (17.18%), $P=.029$.
- Item no.5. Masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly. Were Strongly Disagree 20 (10.41%), Disagree 53 (27.60%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 57 (29.68%), Strongly agree 32 (16.66%), $P=.446$.
- Item no.6. Patients' family members interfere in communication. Were Strongly Disagree 21 (10.93%), Disagree 32 (16.66%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 76 (39.58%), Strongly agree 28 (14.58%), $P=.223$.
- Item no.7. I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures. Were Strongly Disagree 8 (4.16%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 24 (12.55%), Agree 84 (43.75%), Strongly agree 55 (28.64%), $P=.006$.
- Item no.8. I receive support from doctors for effective communication. Were Strongly Disagree 15 (7.81%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 75 (39.06%), Strongly agree 51 (26.56%), $P=.464$.
- Item no.9. I have received training in communication skills. Were Strongly Disagree 3 (1.56%), Disagree 33 (17.18%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 72 (37.5%), Strongly agree 54 (28.12%), $P=.796$.
- Item no.10. Overall, my communication with patients is effective. Were Strongly Disagree 0, Disagree 14 (7.29%), Neutral 14 (7.29%), Agree 49 (25.52%), Strongly agree 114 (59.37%), $P=.012$.

TABLE NO. 9. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH NURSES SUBJECT OF GENDER (RESULT OF PATIENT)

S no	Item	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	P value
1	I understand what nurses tell me about my illness	5 (2.60%)	15 (7.81%)	5 (2.60%)	45 (23.43%)	122 (63.54%)	.177
2	Nurses explain my medicines clearly	4 (2.08%)	9 (4.68%)	8 (4.16%)	80 (41.66%)	91 (47.39%)	.214
3	Nurses give me enough time to ask questions	4 (2.08%)	28 (14.58%)	15 (7.81%)	68 (35.41%)	77 (40.10%)	.064
4	I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses	0	8 (4.16%)	38 (19.79%)	108 (56.25%)	38 (19.79%)	.107
5	Nurses respect my privacy during care	0	13 (6.77%)	10 (5.20%)	82 (42.70%)	87 (45.31%)	.244
6	Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses	6 (3.12%)	37 (19.27%)	19 (9.89%)	93 (48.43%)	37 (19.27%)	.164
7	The Ward environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult	5 (2.60%)	30 (15.62%)	19 (9.89%)	108 (56.25%)	30 (15.62%)	.000
8	Nurses listen to my concerns show care	4 (2.08%)	19 (9.89%)	4 (2.08%)	104 (54.16%)	61 (31.77%)	.005
9	Overall, I am satisfied with nurses' communication	4 (2.08%)	13 (6.77%)	12 (6.25%)	78 (40.62%)	84 (43.75%)	.005

- Item no.01. I understand what nurses tell me about my illness. Were strongly disagree with 5 (2.60%), Disagree 15 (7.81%), Neutral 5 (2.60%), Agree 45 (23.45%), Strongly disagree 122 (63.54%), $p=.177$
- Item no.02. nurses explain my medicines clearly. Were strongly disagree 4 (2.08%), Disagree 9 (4.68%), Neutral 8 (4.16%), Agree 80 (41.66%), Strongly agree 91 (47.39%), $p = .214$.
- Item no.03. nurses give me enough time to ask questions. were Strongly disagree 4 (2.08%), Disagree 28 (14.58%), Neutral 15 (7.81%), Agree 68 (35.41%), Strongly agree 77 (40.10%), $p = .064$.
- Item no.04. I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses. Were Strongly disagree 0, Disagree 8 (4.16%), Neutral 38 (19.79%), Agree 108 (56.25%), Strongly agree 38 (19.79%), $p = .107$.
- Item no.05. nurses respect my privacy during care. Were strongly disagree 0, Disagree 13 (6.77%), Neutral 10 (5.20%), Agree 82 (42.70%), Strongly agree 87 (45.31%), $p=.244$.
- Item no.06. Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses. Were Strongly disagree 6 (3.12%), Disagree 37 (19.27%), Neutral 19 (9.89%), Agree 93 (48.43%), Strongly agree 37 (19.27%), $p = .164$.
- Item no.07. The ward environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult. Were Strongly disagree 5 (2.60%), Disagree 30 (15.62%), Neutral 19 (9.89%), Agree 108 (56.25%), strongly agree 30 (15.62%), $P = .000$.
- Item no.08. nurses listen to my concerns show care. Were Strongly disagree 0, disagree 20 (10.41%), Neutral 4 (2.08%), Agree 107 (55.72%), Strongly agree 61 (31.77%), $p=.299$.
- Item no. 09. Overall, I am satisfied with nurse's communication. Were Strongly disagree 0, Disagree 14 (7.29%), Neutral 13 (6.77%), Agree 79 (41.14%), Strongly agree 86 (44.79%), $p = .763$.

TABLE NO. 10. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH PATIENT SUBJECT OF GENDER (RESULT OF NURSES)

S No	Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	P Value
1	I face language problems while communicating with patients.	29 (15.10%)	31 (16.14%)	46 (23.95%)	66 (34.37%)	20 (10.43%)	.002
2	Heavy workload affects my communication with patients.	17 (8.85%)	30 (15.62%)	35 (18.22%)	86 (44.79%)	24 (12.5%)	.000
3	Cultural or religious differences create difficulties.	10 (5.20%)	48 (25%)	38 (19.79%)	53 (27.60%)	43 (22.39%)	.001
4	The hospital environment (noise, privacy issues) makes communication difficult.	17 (8.85%)	21 (10.93%)	46 (23.95%)	75 (39.06%)	33 (17.18%)	.023
5	Masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly.	20 (10.41%)	53 (27.60%)	30 (15.62%)	57 (29.68%)	32 (16.66%)	.000
6	Patients' family members interfere in communication	21 (10.93%)	32 (16.66%)	35 (18.22%)	76 (39.58%)	28 (14.58%)	.291
7	I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures.	8 (4.16%)	21 (10.93%)	24 (12.5%)	84 (43.75%)	55 (28.64%)	.630

8	I receive support from doctors for effective communication.	15 (7.81%)	21 (10.93%)	30 (15.62%)	75 (39.06%)	51 (26.56%)	.045
9	I have received training in communication skills	3 (1.56%)	33 (17.18%)	30 (15.62%)	72 (37.5%)	54 (28.12%)	.008
10	Overall, my communication with patients is effective	0	14 (7.29%)	14 (7.29%)	49 (25.52%)	114 (59.37%)	.015

- Item no.01. I face language problems while communicating with patients. Were Strongly disagree 29 (15.10%), Disagree 31 (16.14%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 66 (34.37%), Strongly agree 20 (10.43%), $p = .002$.
- Item no.02. Heavy workload affects my communication with patients. Were Strongly disagreed with 17 (8.85%), Disagree 30 (15.62%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 86 (44.79%), Strongly agree 24 (12.5%), $p = .000$.
- Item no.03. cultural or religious differences create difficulties. Were Strongly disagree 10 (5.20%), Disagree 48 (25%), Neutral 38 (19.79%), Agree 53 (27.60%), Strongly agree 43 (22.39%), $p = .001$.
- Item no.04. The hospital environment (noise, privacy issues) makes communication difficult. Were Strongly disagree 17 (8.85%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 75 (39.06%), Strongly agree 33 (17.18%), $p = .023$.
- Item no. 05. Masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly. Were Strongly disagree 20 (10.41%), Disagree 53 (27.60%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 57 (29.68%), Strongly agree 32 (16.66%), $p = .000$.
- Item no.06. patients' family members interfere in communication. Were Strongly disagree 21 (10.39%), Disagree 32 (16.66%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 76 (39.58%), Strongly agree 28 (14.58%), $p = .291$.
- Item no. 07. I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures. Were Strongly disagree 8 (4.16%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 24 (12.5%), Agree 84 (43.75%), Strongly agree 55 (28.64%), $p = .630$.
- Item no.08. I received support from doctors for effective communication. Were Strongly disagree 15 (7.81%), Disagree 21 (10.39%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 75 (39.06%), strongly agree 51 (28.12%), $p = .045$.
- Item no. 09. I have received training in communication skills. Were Strongly disagree 3 (1.56%), Disagree 33 (17.18%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 72 (37.5%), Strongly agree 54 (28.12%), $p = .008$
- Item no.10. Overall, my communication with patients is effective. Were Strongly disagree 0, Disagree 14 (7.29%), Neutral 14 (7.29%), Agree 49 (25.52%), Strongly agree 114 (59.37%), $p = .015$.

TABLE NO. 11. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH NURSES SUBJECT OF MARITAL STATUS (RESULTS OF PATIENTS)

S no	Item	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	P value
1	I understand what nurses tell me about my illness	3 (1.56%)	6 (3.12%)	5 (2.60%)	85 (44.27%)	93 (48.43%)	.005
2	Nurses explain my medicines clearly	7 (3.64%)	2 (1.04%)	5 (2.60%)	84 (43.75%)	94 (48.95%)	.003
3	Nurses give me enough time to ask questions	6 (3.12%)	13 (6.77%)	18 (%)	107 (55.72%)	48 (%)	.013
4	I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses	3 (1.56%)	8 (4.16%)	13 (6.77%)	124 (64.58%)	44 (22.91%)	.005
5	Nurses respect my privacy during care	6 (3.12%)	10 (5.20%)	9 (4.68%)	116 (60.41%)	51 (26.56%)	.005
6	Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses	6 (3.12%)	37 (19.27%)	19 (9.89%)	93 (48.43%)	37 (19.27%)	.003
7	The Ward environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult	6 (3.12%)	20 (10.41%)	26 (13.54%)	94 (48.95%)	46 (23.95%)	.005
8	Nurses listen to my concerns show care	4 (2.08%)	19 (9.89%)	4 (2.08%)	104 (54.16%)	61 (31.77%)	.005
9	Overall, I am satisfied with nurse's communication	4 (2.08%)	13 (6.77%)	12 (6.25%)	78 (40.62%)	84 (43.75%)	.005

- Item no.01. I understand what nurses tell me about my illness. were Strongly disagree 3 (1.56%), Disagree 6 (3.12%), Neutral 5 (2.60%), Agree 85 (44.27%), Strongly agree 93 (48.43%), $p=.005$.
- Item no.02. nurses explain my medicines clearly. Were Strongly disagree 7 (3.64%), Disagree 2 (1.04%), Neutral 5 (2.60%), Agree 84 (43.75%), Strongly agree 94 (48.95%), $p =.003$.
- Item no.03. nurses give me enough time to ask questions. were Strongly disagree 6 (3.12%), Disagree 13 (6.77%), Neutral 18 (9.37%), Agree 107 (55.72%), Strongly agree 48 (25%), $p=.013$.
- Item no.04. I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses. Were Strongly disagree 3(1.56%), Disagree 8 (4.16%), Neutral 13(6.77%), Agree 124(64.58%), Strongly agree 44(22.91%), $p=.005$.
- Item no.05. nurses respect my privacy during care. Were Strongly disagree 6(3.12%), Disagree 10 (5.60%), Neutral 9 (4.68%), Agree 116 (60.41%), strongly agree 51 (26.56%), $p=.005$.
- Item no.06. Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses. Were Strongly disagree 6 (3.12%), Disagree 37 (19.27%), Neutral 19 (9.89%), Agree 93 (48.43%), Strongly agree 37 (19.27%), $P=.003$.
- Item no.07. The environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult. Were Strongly disagree 6 (3.12%), Disagree 20(10.41%), Neutral 26(13.54%), Agree94 (48.95%), Strongly agree 46(23.95%), $P=.005$.
- Item no. 08. Nurses listen to my concerns show care. Were strongly disagree 4(2.08%), Disagree 19 (9.89%), Neutral 4

(2.08%), Agree 104 (54.16%), Strongly agree 61 (31.77%), $P_{=}.005$.

- Item no.09. Overall, I am satisfied with nurse's communication. Were Strongly

disagree 4(2.08%), disagree 13 (6.77%), Neutral 12(6.25%), Agree 78 (40.62%), Strongly agree 84 (43.75%), $P_{=}.005$.

TABLE NO. 12. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH NURSES SUBJECT OF MARITAL STATUS (RESULTS OF NURSES)

S No	Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	P Value
1	I face language problems while communicating with patients.	29 (15.10%)	31 (16.14%)	46 (23.95%)	66 (34.37%)	20 (10.43%)	.000
2	Heavy workload affects my communication with patients.	17 (8.85%)	30 (15.62%)	35 (18.22%)	86 (44.79%)	24 (12.5%)	.000
3	Cultural or religious differences create difficulties.	10 (5.20%)	48 (25%)	38 (19.79%)	53 (27.60%)	43 (22.39%)	.000
4	The hospital environment (noise, privacy issues) makes communication difficult.	17 (8.85%)	21 (10.93%)	46 (23.95%)	75 (39.06%)	33 (17.18%)	.000
5	Masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly.	20 (10.41%)	53 (27.60%)	30 (15.62%)	57 (29.68%)	32 (16.66%)	.000
6	Patients' family members interfere in communication	21 (10.93%)	32 (16.66%)	35 (18.22%)	76 (39.58%)	28 (14.58%)	.000
7	I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures.	8 (4.16%)	21 (10.93%)	24 (12.5%)	84 (43.75%)	55 (28.64%)	.000
8	I receive support from doctors for effective communication.	15 (7.81%)	21 (10.93%)	30 (15.62%)	75 (39.06%)	51 (26.56%)	.000
9	I have received training in communication skills	3 (1.56%)	33 (17.18%)	30 (15.62%)	72 (37.5%)	54 (28.12%)	.016
10	Overall, my communication with patients is effective	0	14 (7.29%)	14 (7.29%)	49 (25.52%)	114 (59.37%)	.000

- Item no.01. I face language problems while communicating with patients. Were Strongly disagree 29 (15.10%), Disagree 31(16.14%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 66 (34.37%), Strongly agree 20 (10.43%), $P_{=}.000$.
- Item no.02. heavy workload affects my communication with patients. Were Strongly disagree 17 (8.85%), Disagree 30 (15.62%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 86 (44.79%), Strongly agree 24 (12.5%), $P_{=}.000$.
- Item no.03. cultural or religious differences create difficulties. Were

Strongly disagree 10 (5.20%), Disagree 48 (25%), Neutral 38 (19.79%), Agree 53 (27.60%), strongly agree 43 (22.39%), $P_{=}.000$.

- Item no.04. The hospital environment (noise, privacy issues) makes communication difficult. Were Strongly disagree 17 (8.85%), Disagree 21 (10.39%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 75 (39.06%), strongly agree 33 (17.18%), $P_{=}.000$.
- Item no.05. masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly. Were Strongly disagree 20 (10.41%), Disagree

- 53 (27.60%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 57 (29.68%), Strongly agree 32 (16.66%), $P = .000$.
- Item no.06. patients' family members interfere in communication. Were Strongly disagree 21 (10.39%), Disagree 32 (16.66%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 76 (39.58%), strongly agree 28 (14.58%), $P = .000$.
 - Item no.07. I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures, were Strongly disagree 8 (4.16%), disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 24 (12.5%), Agree 84 (43.75%), Strongly agree 55 (28.64%), $P = .000$.
 - Item no.08. I receive support from doctors for effective communication skills. Were Strongly disagreed 15 (7.81%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 75 (39.06%), Strongly Agree 51 (26.56%), $P = .000$.
 - Item no.09. I have received training in communication skills. Were Strongly disagreed 3 (1.56%), Disagree 33 (17.18%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 72 (37.5%), Strongly agree 54 (28.12%), $P = .0168$.
 - Item no.10. Overall, my communication with patients is effective. Were Strongly disagree 0, Disagree 14 (7.29%), Neutral 14 (7.29%), Agree 49 (25.52%), Strongly agree 114 (59.37%), $P = .000$.

TABLE NO. 13. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH NURSES SUBJECT OF YEARS OF NURSING EXPERIENCE (RESULTS OF NURSES)

S No	Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	P Value
1	I face language problems while communicating with patients.	29 (15.10%)	31 (16.14%)	46 (23.95%)	66 (34.37%)	20 (10.43%)	.015
2	Heavy workload affects my communication with patients.	17 (8.85%)	30 (15.62%)	35 (18.22%)	86 (44.79%)	24 (12.5%)	.003 ^c
3	Cultural or religious differences create difficulties.	10 (5.20%)	48 (25%)	38 (19.79%)	53 (27.60%)	43 (22.39%)	.716 ^c
4	The hospital environment (noise, privacy issues) makes communication difficult.	17 (8.85%)	21 (10.93%)	46 (23.955)	75 (39.06%)	33 (17.18%)	.040 ^c
5	Masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly.	20 (10.41%)	53 (27.60%)	30 (15.62%)	57 (29.68%)	32 (16.66%)	.737 ^c
6	Patients family members interfere in communication	21 (10.93%)	32 (16.66%)	35 (18.22%)	76 (39.58%)	28 (14.58%)	.015 ^c
7	I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures.	8 (4.16%)	21 (10.93%)	24 (12.5%)	84 (43.75%)	55 (28.64%)	.000 ^c
8	I receive support from doctors for effective communication.	15 (7.81%)	21 (10.93%)	30 (15.62%)	75 (39.06%)	51 (26.56%)	.004 ^c
9	I have received training in communication skills	3 (1.56%)	33 (17.18%)	30 (15.62%)	72 (37.5%)	54 (28.12%)	.227 ^c
10	Overall, my communication with patients is effective	0	14 (7.29%)	14 (7.29%)	49 (25.52%)	114 (59.37%)	.011 ^c

- Item no.1. I face language problems while communicating with patients. Were Strongly Disagree 29 (15.10%), Disagree 31 (16.14%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 66 (34.37%), Strongly agree 20 (10.43%), $P = .015$.
- Item no.2. Heavy workload affects my communication with patients. Were Strongly Disagree 17 (8.85%), Disagree 30 (15.62%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 86 (44.79%), Strongly agree 24 (12.5%), $P = .003$.
- Item no.3. Cultural or religious differences create difficulties. Were Strongly Disagree 10 (5.20%), Disagree 48 (25%), Neutral 38 (19.79%), Agree 53 (27.60%), Strongly agree 43 (22.39%), $P = .716$.
- Item no.4. The hospital environment (noise, privacy, issues) makes communication difficult. Were Strongly Disagree 17 (8.85%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 46 (23.95%), Agree 75 (39.06%), Strongly agree 33 (17.18%), $P = .040$.
- Item no.5. Masks or PPE reduce my ability to communicate clearly. Were Strongly Disagree 20 (10.41%), Disagree 53 (27.60%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 57 (29.68%), Strongly agree 32 (16.66%), $P = .737$.
- Item no.6. Patients' family members interfere in communication. Were Strongly Disagree 21 (10.93%), Disagree 32 (16.66%), Neutral 35 (18.22%), Agree 76 (39.58%), Strongly agree 28 (14.58%), $P = .015$.
- Item no.7. I feel confident in explaining diagnosis, treatment and procedures. Were Strongly Disagree 8 (4.16%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 24 (12.5%), Agree 84 (43.75%), Strongly agree 55 (28.64%), $P = .000$.
- Item no.8. I receive support from doctors for effective communication. Were Strongly Disagree 15 (7.81%), Disagree 21 (10.93%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 75 (39.06%), Strongly agree 51 (26.56%), $P = .004$.
- Item no.9. I have received training in communication skills. Were Strongly Disagree 3 (1.56%), Disagree 33 (17.18%), Neutral 30 (15.62%), Agree 72 (37.5%), Strongly agree 54 (28.12%), $P = .227$.
- Item no.10. Overall, my communication with patients is effective. Were Strongly Disagree 0, Disagree 14 (7.29%), Neutral 14 (7.29%), Agree 49 (25.52%), Strongly agree 114 (59.37%), $P = .011$.

TABLE NO. 14. DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION WITH NURSES SUBJECT OF LENGTH OF STAY IN HOSPITAL (RESULT OF PATIENTS)

S no	Item	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	P value
1	I understand what nurses tell me about my illness	3 (1.56%)	7 (3.64%)	13 (6.77%)	85 (44.27%)	84 (43.75%)	.004 ^c
2	Nurses explain my medicines clearly	5 (2.60%)	13 (6.77%)	7 (3.64%)	92 (47.91%)	75 (39.06%)	.005 ^c
3	Nurses give me enough time to ask questions	8 (4.16%)	14 (7.29%)	10 (5.20%)	112 (58.33%)	48 (25%)	.005 ^c
4	I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses	5 (2.60%)	6 (3.12%)	10 (5.20%)	117 (60.93%)	54 (28.12%)	.003 ^c
5	Nurses respect my privacy during care	5 (2.60%)	8 (4.16%)	14 (7.29%)	115 (59.89%)	50 (26.04%)	.001 ^c
6	Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses	6 (3.12%)	19 (9.89%)	17 (8.85%)	113 (58.85%)	37 (19.27%)	.005 ^c
7	The Ward environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult	5 (2.60%)	30 (15.62%)	19 (9.89%)	108 (56.25%)	30 (15.62%)	.000 ^c
8	Nurses listen to my concerns show care	6 (3.12%)	9 (4.68%)	4 (2.08%)	116 (60.41%)	57 (29.68%)	.001 ^c
9	Overall, I am satisfied with nurses communication	4 (2.08%)	12 (6.25%)	13 (6.77%)	79 (41.14%)	84 (43.75%)	.000 ^c

- Item no.01. I understand what nurses tell me about my illness. Were Strongly disagree 3 (1.56%), Disagree 7 (3.64%), Neutral 13 (6.77%), Agree 85 (44.27%), Strongly agree 84 (43.75%), P₌.004.

- Item no. 02. Nurses explain my medicines clearly. Were Strongly disagree 5 (2.60%), Disagree 13(6.77%), Neutral 7 (3.64%), Agree 92 (47.91%), Strongly agree 75 (39.06%), P₌.005.

- Item no. 03. Nurses give me enough time to ask questions. Strongly disagree 8(4.16%), Disagree 14(7.29%), Neutral 10 (5.20%), Agree 112 (58.33%), Strongly agree 48 (25%), P₌.005.

- Item no.04. I feel comfortable sharing personal problems with nurses. Were Strongly Disagree 5(2.60%), Disagree 6(3.12%), Neutral 10 (5.20%), Agree 117(60.93%), Strongly agree 54(28.12%), P₌ .003.

- Item no.05. Nurses respect my privacy

- during care. Were Strongly Disagree 5(2.60%), Disagree 8(4.16%), Neutral 14(7.29%), Agree 115(59.89%), Strongly agree 50(26.04%), P₌.001.

- Item no.6. Language differences make it hard for me to understand nurses. Were Strongly Disagree 6 (3.12%), Disagree 19(9.89%), Neutral 17(8.85%), Agree 113(58.85%), Strongly agree 37 (19.27%), P₌.005.

- Item no.7. The ward environment (noise busy staff) makes communication difficult. Were Strongly Disagree 5 (2.60%), Disagree 30 (15.62%), Neutral 19 (9.89%), Agree 108 (56.25%), Strongly agree 30 (15.62%), P₌.000.

- Item no.8. Nurses listen to my concerns show care. Were Strongly Disagree 6(3.12%), Disagree 9(4.68%), Neutral 4 (2.08%), Agree 116 (60.41%), Strongly agree 57(29.68%), P₌.001.

- Item no.9. Overall, I am satisfied with

nurses communication. Were Strongly Disagree 4(2.08%), Disagree 12(6.25%), Neutral 13 (6.77%), Agree 79 (41.14%), Strongly agree 84 (43.75%), $P=0.000$.

Discussion:

This study conducted at People Medical College Hospital Nawabshah, the aim of this study to determine the barriers between the nurse and patient encounters during the patient management and hospitalization. In this study majority nurses were male (55.21%), and patient were female (78.13%), which is comparable with study by Atghae Kordkolae Z et al.2024 reported that majority of nurses were (male), there fore gender is also main determinant in health care settings.¹⁹

Distribution of age of subject among nurses and patients were, nurses mean (37.9, S.D + 05), and patient mean age (42.9, S.D + 15) which is comparable with study by Nada Mahmood Abdulla et al. 2022 reported mean age of nursing and Patient were, (36.8, S. D± 11.6).²

Distribution of subject of marital status patients were, married (65.6%), and nurses were, married (83.9%), majority of married nurses and patients. which is comparable with study by Nada Mahmood Abdulla et al.2022 reported that married (77.9%). In this study majority of married persons. ²

Duration of hospital stay patents among study subjects reported patients were, mean (5.31, S. D±3.9), which comparable with study by FERRARI et al.2021 reported mean (2, S. D±1) and further comparable study by K. McGilton et al.2025 reported mean (65.3 S.D ±132).²⁰²¹

Distribution of subject of years of nursing experience among study reported mean (7.4, S. D± 5.9) years, which is comparable with study by FERRARI et al.2021 reported mean was, (15 S. D±14) years, and further which is comparable with study by K. McGilton et al.2025 reported mean (20.2 S.D±9.4), and another which comparable with study by Farasat Ardalan et al. 2018, reported mean (9.41 S. D±7.51). ^{20 2221}

Distribution of subjects of average number of patients per shift nurses were, mean (22.3 S. D± 23.7), which comparable with study by Dhungana

al. 2020 mean (3.78 S.D ±1.25).²³

In this study language barrier / problem were commonly noticed between the nurse and patients, were majority of 93(48.43%, $P = .003$) is agree, which comparable with study by Farasat Ardalan et.al.2018 supported that language barriers is commonly noticed among nurses and patient , also compared with another study reported that language berries is common problem between nurses and patients were (2.67 S.D±1.06).²²

In this study religious differences between nurses and patients create difficulties were, majority of agree is 53(27.60 %, $P=0.001$), which comparable with study by Moges Wubneh et.al.2020 majority of were disagree, disagree 215(58.1%), mean 1.79. ¹⁵

In this study heavy workload or time management affects communication between nurses and patients where, majority of agree is 86(44.79%, $P=0.000$), which comparable with study by Moges Wubneh et.al.2020, majority agree 299(80.8%), mean 2.66.¹⁵

In this study the ward environment noise makes communication difficulties majority of agree 75(39.06%, $P = .000$), which comparable with study by Dhungana et al. 2020, mean (4.09 S. D±1.04).²³

In this study PPE reduce communicate clearly were majority of agree is 57(29.68%, $P= .000$), which comparable with study by Dhungana et al. 2020 majority of agree (3.56 S. D±1.23), this study is supported.²³

In this study family member interfere in communication noticed between nurses and patients were majority reported agree is (39.58%, $P= .015$),which comparable with study Roohangiz Norouzinia et al.2015 (2.39 S.D±0.69, $p= 0.026$), this study is supported because statistically significant. ¹³

In this study training in communication skills reported between nurses and patients were majority of agree is (73.5%, $p= .000$), which comparable with study Ataee kordkolae Z et al.2024 agree is (102.90 S. D±14.31).¹⁹

In this study explains clearly communication between nurses and patients reported strongly agree (48.95%, $P= .003$), which comparable study

with LOTFI et al. 2019, (3.18, S.D±1.31).24

Conclusion

Communication barriers, such as language and workload issues, affect the nurses-patient's relationships at PMCH Nawabshah, and addressing these challenges can improve the patient satisfaction and the care quality. The study's findings are useful for enhancing communication strategies at PMCH Nawabshah and similar hospitals.

Recommendation:

The study recommends improving communication at PMCH Nawabshah by offering language support for nurses providing the cultural sensitivity training, reducing nurse workload, and using technologies like communication apps. Involving families and ensuring a quieter environment can also help.

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